

Analytical corpus for
‘Research on portfolios in teacher education: a systematic review’

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1. Introduction

This paper contains the bibliographic details of the corpus of literature identified by criteria for the analysis of research on portfolios (Feder and Cramer, 2023). We proceeded in the following way to create the literature corpus (see Fig. 1) (Feder and Cramer, 2023): ‘Two relevant major research databases (*ERIC* and *Web of Science*) were systematically searched using predetermined search paths (Figure 1) to identify the corpus of journal articles used for the analysis.

Figure 1. Flowchart showing analysis corpus generation

Note. P1 = Period 1 (2005–2017; date of search: 27th October 2017); P2 = Period 2 (2017–2021; date of search: 2nd December 2021).

Monographs were excluded from the literature search, as they provide information much more detailed and in a non-comparable, lower density. To ensure that the analysis focused on a long period of research, articles published since 2005 (beginning of a noticeable increase in publications on portfolios regarding teacher education) and indexed in the databases by October 2017 (start of the analyses of this sample in different sub-studies) were included (Period 1). At the end of the research process, the literature search was expanded to include additional articles indexed by December 2021 (Period 2). All analyses were then updated accordingly to include the most recent state of the art.

In Period 1 a total of 693 texts were identified; 228 texts were selected additionally in Period 2. Subsequently, 179 texts remained in the analytical corpus in Period 1, complemented by 67 in Period 2, leading to a total sample for $N = 246$ texts for the analysis [...]. First, duplicates that appeared in both databases were excluded. Besides a restriction to peer-reviewed journals as an inclusion-criteria, there was no limitation to quality criteria in advance, as considering the purpose of the study, an extensive analysis of the heterogeneous field of research, it is particularly essential to incorporate a wide database.'

2. Bibliographical data

Table 1. Bibliographical data of the analytical corpus

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
1	Adadan & Oner	2018	Examining Preservice Teachers' Reflective Thinking Skills in the Context of Web-Based Portfolios: The Role of Metacognitive Awareness	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Adadan, E., & Oner, D. (2018). Examining Preservice Teachers' Reflective Thinking Skills in the Context of Web-Based Portfolios: The Role of Metacognitive Awareness. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 43(11), 26–50.
2	Admiraal & Berry	2016	Video Narratives to Assess Student Teachers' Competence as New Teachers	Teachers and Teaching	Admiraal, W., & Berry, A. (2016). Video Narratives to Assess Student Teachers' Competence as New Teachers. <i>Teachers and Teaching</i> , 22(1), 21–34.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
3	Admiraal, Hoeksma, van de Kamp & van Duin	2011	Assessment of Teacher Competence Using Video Portfolios: Reliability, Construct Validity, and Consequential Validity	Teaching and Teacher Education	Admiraal, W., Hoeksma, M., van de Kamp, M.-T., & van Duin, G. (2011). Assessment of Teacher Competence Using Video Portfolios: Reliability, Construct Validity, and Consequential Validity. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 27(6), 1019–1028.
4	Admiraal, Janssen, Huizenga, Kranenburg, Taconis & Corda	2014	E-Assessment of Student-Teachers' Competence as New Teachers	Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	Admiraal, W., Janssen, T., Huizenga, J., Kranenburg, F., Taconis, R., & Corda, A. (2014). E-Assessment of Student-Teachers' Competence as New Teachers. <i>Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 13(4), 21–29.
5	Aksit	2016	Implementing Portfolios in Teacher Training: Why We Use Them and Why We Should Use Them	Eurasian Journal of Educational Research	Aksit, F. (2016). Implementing Portfolios in Teacher Training: Why We Use Them and Why We Should Use Them. <i>Eurasian Journal of Educational Research</i> , 97–114.
6	Alajmi	2019	The impact of E-Portfolio use on the development of professional standards and life skills of students: A case study.	Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues	Alajmi, M. M. (2019). The impact of E-Portfolio use on the development of professional standards and life skills of students: A case study. <i>Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues</i> , 6(4), 1714–1735.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
7	Allard, Mayer & Moss	2014	Authentically Assessing Graduate Teaching: Outside and beyond Neo-Liberal Constructs	Australian Educational Researcher	Allard, A. C., Mayer, D., & Moss, J. (2014). Authentically Assessing Graduate Teaching: Outside and beyond Neo-Liberal Constructs. <i>Australian Educational Researcher</i> , 41(4), 425–443.
8	Almusharraf	2020	Student Teachers' Development of Reflective Practice Concerning Teaching Philosophy and Peer Observations	Arab World English Journal	Almusharraf, A. M. (2020). Student Teachers' Development of Reflective Practice Concerning Teaching Philosophy and Peer Observations. <i>Arab World English Journal</i> , 11(4), 547–564.
9	Alshawi & Alshumaimeri	2017	Teacher Electronic Portfolio and Its Relation to EFL Student Teacher Performance and Attitude	International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies	Alshawi, A. T., & Alshumaimeri, Y. A. (2017). Teacher Electronic Portfolio and Its Relation to EFL Student Teacher Performance and Attitude. <i>International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies</i> , 5(1), 42–54.
10	Alsina Ayllon, Colomer, Fernandez-Pena, Fullana, Pallisera & Serra	2017	Improving and evaluating reflective narratives: A rubric for higher education students	Teaching and Teacher Education	Alsina, A., Ayllon, S., Colomer, J., Fernandez-Pena, R., Fullana, J., Pallisera, M., Serra, L. (2017). Improving and evaluating reflective narratives: A rubric for higher education students. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 63, 148–158.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
11	An & Wilder	2010	A Bottom-Up Approach for Implementing Electronic Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program	Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education	An, H., & Wilder, H. (2010). A Bottom-Up Approach for Implementing Electronic Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program. <i>Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education</i> , 26(3), 84–91.
12	Anunti, Vuopala & Rusanen	2020	A Portfolio Model for the Teaching and Learning of GIS Competencies in an Upper Secondary School: A Case Study from a Finnish Geomedia Course	Review of international Geographic Education	Anunti, H., Vuopala, E., & Rusanen, J. (2020). A Portfolio Model for the Teaching and Learning of GIS Competencies in an Upper Secondary School: A Case Study from a Finnish Geomedia Course. <i>Review of international Geographic Education</i> , 10(3), 262–282.
13	Arnold & Mundy	2020	Praxis pedagogy in teacher education	Smart Learning Environments	Arnold, J., & Mundy, B. (2020). Praxis pedagogy in teacher education. <i>Smart Learning Environments</i> , 7(1). 1–14.
14	Arnott & Vignola	2018	The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) in French immersion teacher education A focus on the language portfolio	Journal of Immersion and Content-Based Language Education	Arnott, S., & Vignola, M. J. (2018). The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) in French immersion teacher education A focus on the language portfolio. <i>Journal of Immersion and Content-Based Language Education</i> , 6(2), 321–345.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
15	Austin & Berg	2020	A Within-Program Analysis of edTPA Score Reliability, Validity, and Utility	Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education	Austin, J. R., & Berg, M. H. (2020). A Within-Program Analysis of edTPA Score Reliability, Validity, and Utility. <i>Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education</i> (226), 46–65.
16	Avraamidou & Zembal-Saul	2006	Exploring the Influence of Web-Based Portfolio Development on Learning to Teach Elementary Science	AACE Journal	Avraamidou, L., & Zembal-Saul, C. (2006). Exploring the Influence of Web-Based Portfolio Development on Learning to Teach Elementary Science. <i>AACE Journal</i> , 14(2), 178–205.
17	Ayan & Seferoglu	2011	Using electronic portfolios to promote reflective thinking in language teacher education	Educational Studies	Ayan, D., & Seferoglu, G. (2011). Using electronic portfolios to promote reflective thinking in language teacher education. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 37(5), 513–521.
18	Bader, Burner, Iversen & Varga	2019	Student perspectives on formative feedback as part of writing portfolios	Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education	Bader, M., Burner, T., Iversen, S. H., & Varga, Z. (2019). Student perspectives on formative feedback as part of writing portfolios. <i>Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education</i> , 44(7), 1017–1028.
19	Baer, Cavill & Daher	2020	Zip Sass and Spitfire: Understanding What Administrators Want to See in Art Teacher Candidate Portfolios	The Professional Educator	Baer, S. A., Cavill, W., Jr., & Daher, T. (2020). Zip Sass and Spitfire: Understanding What Administrators Want to See in Art Teacher Candidate Portfolios. <i>The Professional Educator</i> , 43(1), 1–14.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
20	Bairral & dos Santos	2012	E-Portfolio Improving Learning in Mathematics Pre-Service Teacher	Digital Education Review	Bairral, M. A., & dos Santos, R. T. (2012). E-Portfolio Improving Learning in Mathematics Pre-Service Teacher. <i>Digital Education Review</i> . 1–12.
21	Banister, Vannatta & Ross	2006	Testing Electronic Portfolio Systems in a Teacher Education: Finding the Right Fit	Action in Teacher Education	Banister, S., Vannatta, R. A., & Ross, C. (2006). Testing Electronic Portfolio Systems in a Teacher Education: Finding the Right Fit. <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 27(4), 81–90.
22	Bannink	2009	How to Capture Growth? – Video Narratives as an Instrument for Assessment in Teacher Education	Teaching and Teacher Education	Bannink, A. (2009). How to Capture Growth? – Video Narratives as an Instrument for Assessment in Teacher Education. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 25(2), 244–250.
23	Bartlett & Sherry	2006	Two Views of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Non-Technology Undergraduates and Technology Graduate Students	International Journal of Instructional Media	Bartlett, A., & Sherry, A. C. (2006). Two Views of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Non-Technology Undergraduates and Technology Graduate Students. <i>International Journal of Instructional Media</i> , 33(3), 245–253.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
24	Bataineh, Al-Karasneh, Al-Barakat & Bataineh	2007	Jordanian Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions of the Portfolio as a Reflective Learning Tool	Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education	Bataineh, R. F., Al-Karasneh, S. M., Al-Barakat, A. A., & Bataineh, R. F. (2007). Jordanian Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions of the Portfolio as a Reflective Learning Tool. <i>Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 35(4), 435–454.
25	Beck, Livne & Bear	2005	Teachers' Self-Assessment of the Effects of Formative and Summative Electronic Portfolios on Professional Development	European Journal of Teacher Education	Beck, R. J., Livne, N. L., & Bear, S. L. (2005). Teachers' Self-Assessment of the Effects of Formative and Summative Electronic Portfolios on Professional Development. <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 28(3), 221–244.
26	Bergil & Sariçoban	2017	The Use of EPOSTL to Determine the Self-Efficacy of Prospective EFL Teachers: Raising Awareness in English Language Teacher Education	Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies	Bergil, A. S., & Sariçoban, A. (2017). The Use of EPOSTL to Determine the Self-Efficacy of Prospective EFL Teachers: Raising Awareness in English Language Teacher Education. <i>Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies</i> , 13(1), 399–411.
27	Berrill & Addison	2010	Repertoires of Practice: Re-Framing Teaching Portfolios	Teaching and Teacher Education	Berrill, D. P., & Addison, E. (2010). Repertoires of Practice: Re-Framing Teaching Portfolios. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 26(5), 1178–1185.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
28	BhatnagarKim & Many	2017	An Instrument to Study State-Wide Implementation of edTPA: Validating the Levels of edTPA Integration Survey	Journal of Research in Education	Bhatnagar, R., Kim, J., & Many, J. E. (2017). An Instrument to Study State-Wide Implementation of edTPA: Validating the Levels of edTPA Integration Survey. <i>Journal of Research in Education</i> , 27(1), 24–33.
29	Bintz & Shake	2005	From University to Classrooms: A Preservice Teachers' Writing Portfolio Program and Its Impact on Instruction in Teaching Strategies for Writing Portfolios in the Classroom	Reading Horizons	Bintz, W., & Shake, M. (2005). From University to Classrooms: A Preservice Teachers' Writing Portfolio Program and Its Impact on Instruction in Teaching Strategies for Writing Portfolios in the Classroom. <i>Reading Horizons</i> , 45(3), 217–233.
30	Birgin	2011	Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers' Views on the Use of Portfolios in Their Education as an Alternative Assessment Method	Educational Research and Reviews	Birgin, O. (2011). Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers' Views on the Use of Portfolios in Their Education as an Alternative Assessment Method. <i>Educational Research and Reviews</i> , 6(11), 710–721.
31	Blackley, Bennett & Sheffield	2017	Purpose-Built, Web-Based Professional Portfolios: Reflective, Developmental and Showcase	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Blackley, S., Bennett, D., & Sheffield, R. (2017). Purpose-Built, Web-Based Professional Portfolios: Reflective, Developmental and Showcase. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 42(5), 1–17.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
32	Boulton	2014	ePortfolios beyond Pre-Service Teacher Education: A New Dawn?	European Journal of Teacher Education	Boulton, H. (2014). ePortfolios beyond Pre-Service Teacher Education: A New Dawn? <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 37(3), 374–389.
33	Brandes & Boskic	2008	Eportfolios: From Description to Analysis	International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning	Brandes, G. M., & Boskic, N. (2008). Eportfolios: From Description to Analysis. <i>International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning</i> , 9(2), 1–17.
34	Buchholtz,Kro sanke, Orschulik & Vorhölter	2018	Combining and Integrating Formative and Summative Assessment in Mathematics Teacher Education	The International Journal on Mathematics Education	Buchholtz, N. F., Krosanke, N., Orschulik, A. B., & Vorhölter, K. (2018). Combining and Integrating Formative and Summative Assessment in Mathematics Teacher Education. <i>The International Journal on Mathematics Education</i> , 50(4), 715–728.
35	Burns & Haight	2005	Psychometric Properties and Instructional Utility of Assessing Special Education Teacher Candidate Knowledge with Portfolios	Teacher Education and Special Education	Burns, M. K., & Haight, S. L. (2005). Psychometric Properties and Instructional Utility of Assessing Special Education Teacher Candidate Knowledge with Portfolios. <i>Teacher Education and Special Education</i> , 28, 185–194.

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36	Byrd	2017	Challenges to Implementing a New Technology in Teacher Education. Phase One: 'Meaningful' Digital Reflections	Teacher Education Advancement Network Journal	Byrd, J. (2017). Challenges to Implementing a New Technology in Teacher Education. Phase One: 'Meaningful' Digital Reflections. <i>Teacher Education Advancement Network Journal</i> , 9(2). 76–85.
37	Caceres, Chamoso & Azcarate	2010	Analysis of the Revisions that Pre-Service Teachers of Mathematics Make of Their Own Project Included in Their Learning Portfolio	Teaching and Teacher Education	Caceres, M. J., Chamoso, J. M., & Azcarate, P. (2010). Analysis of the Revisions that Pre-Service Teachers of Mathematics Make of Their Own Project Included in Their Learning Portfolio. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 26(5), 1186–1195.
38	Cain & Campbell	2021	Creating Greater Awareness of the Australian Professional Standards for Teachers in Initial Teacher Education	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Cain, M., & Campbell, C. (2021). Creating Greater Awareness of the Australian Professional Standards for Teachers in Initial Teacher Education. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 46(7), 70–85.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
39	Cakir & Balcikanli	2012	The Use of the European Portfolio for Student Teachers of Languages (EPOSTL) to Foster Teacher Autonomy: English Language Teaching (ELT) Student Teachers' and Teacher Trainers' Views	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Cakir, A., & Balcikanli, C. (2012). The Use of the European Portfolio for Student Teachers of Languages (EPOSTL) to Foster Teacher Autonomy: English Language Teaching (ELT) Student Teachers' and Teacher Trainers' Views. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 37(3), 1–16.
40	Capraro	2006	Electronic Teaching Portfolios: Technology Skills + Portfolio Development = Powerful Preservice Teachers?	Teacher Education and Practice	Capraro, M. M. (2006). Electronic Teaching Portfolios: Technology Skills + Portfolio Development = Powerful Preservice Teachers? <i>Teacher Education and Practice</i> , 19(3), 380–390.
41	Carl & Strydom	2017	e-Portfolio as Reflection Tool during Teaching Practice: The Interplay between Contextual and Dispositional Variables	South African Journal of Education	Carl, A., & Strydom, S. (2017). e-Portfolio as Reflection Tool during Teaching Practice: The Interplay between Contextual and Dispositional Variables. <i>South African Journal of Education</i> , 37(1), 1–10.
42	Carpenter, Apostel & Hyndman	2012	Developing a Model for ePortfolio Design: A Studio Approach	International Journal of ePortfolio	Carpenter, R., Apostel, S., & Hyndman, J. O. (2012). Developing a Model for ePortfolio Design: A Studio Approach. <i>International Journal of ePortfolio</i> , 2(2), 163–172.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
43	Chamoso & Caceres	2009	Analysis of the Reflections of Student-Teachers of Mathematics When Working with Learning Portfolios in Spanish University Classrooms	Teaching and Teacher Education	Chamoso, J. M., & Caceres, M. J. (2009). Analysis of the Reflections of Student-Teachers of Mathematics When Working with Learning Portfolios in Spanish University Classrooms. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 25(1), 198–206.
44	Chamoso, Caceres & Azcarate	2012	Reflection on the Teaching-Learning Process in the Initial Training of Teachers. Characterization of the Issues on Which Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers Reflect	Teaching and Teacher Education	Chamoso, J. M., Caceres, M. J., & Azcarate, P. (2012). Reflection on the Teaching-Learning Process in the Initial Training of Teachers. Characterization of the Issues on Which Pre-Service Mathematics Teachers Reflect. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 28(2), 154–164.
45	Chen	2017	Developing Electronic Teaching Portfolios: A Way to Success for Preservice Teachers	Journal of Technology and Chinese Language Teaching	Chen, D. (2017). Developing Electronic Teaching Portfolios: A Way to Success for Preservice Teachers. <i>Journal of Technology and Chinese Language Teaching</i> , 8(1), 66–85.
46	Chetcuti, Murphy & Grima	2006	The Formative and Summative Uses of a Professional Development Portfolio: A Maltese Case Study	Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy and Practice	Chetcuti, D., Murphy, P., & Grima, G. (2006). The Formative and Summative Uses of a Professional Development Portfolio: A Maltese Case Study. <i>Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy and Practice</i> , 13(1), 97–112.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
47	Ching, Yang, Baek & Baldwin	2016	Enhancing Graduate Students' Reflection in E-Portfolios Using the TPACK Framework	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Ching, Y.-H., Yang, D., Baek, Y., & Baldwin, S. (2016). Enhancing Graduate Students' Reflection in E-Portfolios Using the TPACK Framework. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 32(5), 108–122.
48	Chittum	2018	The Theory-to-Practice ePortfolio: An Assignment to Facilitate Motivation and Higher Order Thinking	International Journal of ePortfolio	Chittum, J. R. (2018). The Theory-to-Practice ePortfolio: An Assignment to Facilitate Motivation and Higher Order Thinking. <i>International Journal of ePortfolio</i> , 8(1), 27–42.
49	Chuang	2010	Weblog-Based Electronic Portfolios for Student Teachers in Taiwan	Educational Technology Research and Development	Chuang, H.-H. (2010). Weblog-Based Electronic Portfolios for Student Teachers in Taiwan. <i>Educational Technology Research and Development</i> , 58(2), 211–227.
50	Chung & van Es	2014	Pre-Service Teachers' Use of Tools to Systematically Analyze Teaching and Learning	Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice	Chung, H. Q., & van Es, E. A. (2014). Pre-Service Teachers' Use of Tools to Systematically Analyze Teaching and Learning. <i>Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice</i> , 20(2), 113–135.
51	Chye, Zhou, Koh & Liu	2019	Using e-portfolios to facilitate reflection: Insights from an activity theoretical analysis	Teaching and Teacher Education	Chye, S., Zhou, M. M., Koh, C., & Liu, W. C. (2019). Using e-portfolios to facilitate reflection: Insights from an activity theoretical analysis. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 85, 24–35.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
52	Chye, Zhou, Koh & Liu	2021	Levels of reflection in student teacher digital portfolios: a matter of sociocultural context?	Reflective Practice	Chye, S., Zhou, M. M., Koh, C., & Liu, W. C. (2021). Levels of reflection in student teacher digital portfolios: a matter of sociocultural context? <i>Reflective Practice</i> , 22(5), 577–599.
53	Ciesielkiewicz	2019	The use of e-portfolios in higher education: From the students' perspective	Issues in Educational Research	Ciesielkiewicz, M. (2019). The use of e-portfolios in higher education: From the students' perspective. <i>Issues in Educational Research</i> , 29(3), 649–667.
54	Ciesielkiewicz	2019	Education for employability: the ePortfolio from school principals' perspective	On the Horizon	Ciesielkiewicz, M. (2019). Education for employability: the ePortfolio from school principals' perspective. <i>On the Horizon</i> , 27(1), 46–56.
55	Cimer	2011	The Effect of Portfolios on Students' Learning: Student Teachers' Views	European Journal of Teacher Education	Cimer, S. O. (2011). The Effect of Portfolios on Students' Learning: Student Teachers' Views. <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 34(2), 161–176.
56	Cindric, Andracka, & Bilic-Stefan	2015	Raising Students' Awareness of Teaching Competences by Means of the European Portfolio for Student Teachers of Languages	Croatian Journal of Education	Cindric, I., Andracka, M., & Bilic-Stefan, M. (2015). Raising Students' Awareness of Teaching Competences by Means of the European Portfolio for Student Teachers of Languages. <i>Croatian Journal of Education</i> , 17, 117–136.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
57	Crichton & Kopp	2008	The Value of eJournals to Support ePortfolio Development for Assessment in Teacher Education	Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology	Crichton, S., & Kopp, G. (2008). The Value of eJournals to Support ePortfolio Development for Assessment in Teacher Education. <i>Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology</i> , 34(3). 1–10.
58	Cronenberg, Harrison, Korson, Jones, Murray-Everett, Parrish & Johnston-Parsons	2016	Trouble with the edTPA: Lessons Learned from a Narrative Self-Study	Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education	Cronenberg, S., Harrison, D., Korson, S., Jones, A., Murray-Everett, N. C., Parrish, M., & Johnston-Parsons, M. (2016). Trouble with the edTPA: Lessons Learned from a Narrative Self-Study. <i>Journal of Inquiry and Action in Education</i> , 8(1), 109–134.
59	Darling-Hammond, Newton & Wei	2010	Evaluating Teacher Education Outcomes: A Study of the Stanford Teacher Education Programme	Journal of Education for Teaching	Darling-Hammond, L., Newton, X., & Wei, R. C. (2010). Evaluating Teacher Education Outcomes: A Study of the Stanford Teacher Education Programme. <i>Journal of Education for Teaching</i> , 36(4), 369–388.
60	De Voto & Thomas	2020	Cultural Sensemaking and the Implementation of edTPA Technological Tools: Lessons for the Field	Educational Technology Research and Development	De Voto, C., & Thomas, M. K. (2020). Cultural Sensemaking and the Implementation of edTPA Technological Tools: Lessons for the Field. <i>Educational Technology Research and Development</i> , 68(5), 2729–2751.

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61	DeCoursey	2020	Behavioural intention of Pacific Island pre-service teachers to use digital portfolios	International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning	DeCoursey, C. A. (2020). Behavioural intention of Pacific Island pre-service teachers to use digital portfolios. <i>International Journal of Technology Enhanced Learning</i> , 12(2), 161–179.
62	Denney, Grier & Buchanan	2012	Establishing a Portfolio Assessment Framework for Pre-Service Teachers: A Multiple Perspectives Approach	Teaching in Higher Education	Denney, M. K., Grier, J. M., & Buchanan, M. (2012). Establishing a Portfolio Assessment Framework for Pre-Service Teachers: A Multiple Perspectives Approach. <i>Teaching in Higher Education</i> , 17(4), 425–437.
63	Denton	2012	Improving the Quality of Evidence-Based Writing Entries in Electronic Portfolios	International Journal of ePortfolio	Denton, D. W. (2012). Improving the Quality of Evidence-Based Writing Entries in Electronic Portfolios. <i>International Journal of ePortfolio</i> , 2(2), 187–197.
64	Denton & Wicks	2013	Implementing Electronic Portfolios through Social Media Platforms: Steps and Student Perceptions	Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks	Denton, D. W., & Wicks, D. (2013). Implementing Electronic Portfolios through Social Media Platforms: Steps and Student Perceptions. <i>Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks</i> , 17(1), 125–135.

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65	Derham & DiPerna	2007	Digital Professional Portfolios of Preservice Teaching: An Initial Study of Score Reliability and Validity	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Derham, C., & DiPerna, J. (2007). Digital Professional Portfolios of Preservice Teaching: An Initial Study of Score Reliability and Validity. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 15(3), 363–381.
66	Dervin & Hahl	2015	Developing a Portfolio of Intercultural Competences in Teacher Education: The Case of a Finnish International Programme	Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research	Dervin, F., & Hahl, K. (2015). Developing a Portfolio of Intercultural Competences in Teacher Education: The Case of a Finnish International Programme. <i>Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research</i> , 59(1), 95–109.
67	Dikici	2009	An Application of Digital Portfolio with the Peer, Self and Instructor Assessments in Art Education	Eurasian Journal of Educational Research	Dikici, A. (2009). An Application of Digital Portfolio with the Peer, Self and Instructor Assessments in Art Education. <i>Eurasian Journal of Educational Research</i> , 9(36), 91–108.
68	Domene-Martos, Rodriguez-Gallego, Caldevilla-Domingue & Barrientos-Baez	2021	The Use of Digital Portfolio in Higher Education before and during the COVID-19 Pandemic	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Domene-Martos, S., Rodriguez-Gallego, M., Caldevilla-Dominguez, D., & Barrientos-Baez, A. (2021). The Use of Digital Portfolio in Higher Education before and during the COVID-19 Pandemic. <i>International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health</i> , 18(20). 1–15.

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69	Donlon	2019	The use of a custom-built online environment for communication with and support of student-teachers during school placement	Teaching Education	Donlon, E. (2019). The use of a custom-built online environment for communication with and support of student-teachers during school placement. <i>Teaching Education, 30</i> (1), 1–15.
70	Dreyer	2015	Reliability of Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) Assessments for Teaching Practice Courses in Open Distance Electronic Learning (ODEL)	International Journal of Educational Sciences	Dreyer, J. M. (2015). Reliability of Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) Assessments for Teaching Practice Courses in Open Distance Electronic Learning (ODEL). <i>International Journal of Educational Sciences, 8</i> (1), 111–117.
71	Duckor, Castellano, Tellez, Wihardini, & Wilson	2014	Examining the Internal Structure Evidence for the Performance Assessment for California Teachers: A Validation Study of the Elementary Literacy Teaching Event for Tier I Teacher Licensure	Journal of Teacher Education	Duckor, B., Castellano, K. E., Tellez, K., Wihardini, D., & Wilson, M. (2014). Examining the Internal Structure Evidence for the Performance Assessment for California Teachers: A Validation Study of the Elementary Literacy Teaching Event for Tier I Teacher Licensure. <i>Journal of Teacher Education, 65</i> (5), 402–420.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
72	Dysthe & Engelsen	2011	Portfolio practices in Higher Education in Norway in an International Perspective: Macro-, Meso- and Micro-level Influences	Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education	Dysthe, O., & Engelsen, K. S. (2011). Portfolio practices in Higher Education in Norway in an International Perspective: Macro-, Meso- and Micro-level Influences. <i>Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education</i> , 36(1), 63–79.
73	Ebil, Salleh & Shahrill	2020	The use of E-portfolio for self-reflection to promote learning: a case of TVET students	Education and Information Technologies	Ebil, S. H., Salleh, S. M., & Shahrill, M. (2020). The use of E-portfolio for self-reflection to promote learning: a case of TVET students. <i>Education and Information Technologies</i> , 25(6), 5797–5814.
74	Elliott, Daily, Fredricks & Graham	2008	Transitioning from Students to Professionals: Using a Writing across the Curriculum Model to Scaffold Portfolio Development	Teacher Educator	Elliott, L., Daily, N. L., Fredricks, L., & Graham, M. S. (2008). Transitioning from Students to Professionals: Using a Writing across the Curriculum Model to Scaffold Portfolio Development. <i>Teacher Educator</i> , 43(1), 46–58.
75	Farrelly & Kaplin	2019	Using Student Feedback to Inform Change within a Community College Teacher Education Program's ePortfolio Initiative	Community College Enterprise	Farrelly, D., & Kaplin, D. (2019). Using Student Feedback to Inform Change within a Community College Teacher Education Program's ePortfolio Initiative. <i>Community College Enterprise</i> , 25(2), 9–38.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
76	Fidalgo & Thormann	2019	Student and Instructor Opinions about Using ePortfolios to Learn Information Literacy Skills	Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia	Fidalgo, P., & Thormann, J. (2019). Student and Instructor Opinions about Using ePortfolios to Learn Information Literacy Skills. <i>Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia</i> , 28(2), 165–191.
77	Fiedler, Mullen & Finnegan	2009	Portfolios in Context: A Comparative Study in Two Preservice Teacher Education Programs	Journal of Research on Technology in Education	Fiedler, R. L., Mullen, L., & Finnegan, M. (2009). Portfolios in Context: A Comparative Study in Two Preservice Teacher Education Programs. <i>Journal of Research on Technology in Education</i> , 42(2), 99–122.
78	Foong, Nor & Nolan	2018	Individual and collective reflection: Deepening early childhood pre-service teachers' reflective thinking during practicum	Australasian Journal of Early Childhood	Foong, L., Nor, M. B. M., & Nolan, A. (2018). Individual and collective reflection: Deepening early childhood pre-service teachers' reflective thinking during practicum. <i>Australasian Journal of Early Childhood</i> , 43(1), 43–51.
79	Frisch	2019	Use of a "Hybrid" Science Notebook by Preservice Elementary Education Teachers: Combining Paper and Digital Tools	Journal of Science Teacher Education	Frisch, J. K. (2019). Use of a "Hybrid" Science Notebook by Preservice Elementary Education Teachers: Combining Paper and Digital Tools. <i>Journal of Science Teacher Education</i> , 30(6), 567–582.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
80	Gallant & Mayer	2012	Teacher performance assessment in teacher education: an example in Malaysia	Journal of Education for Teaching	Gallant, A., & Mayer, D. (2012). Teacher performance assessment in teacher education: an example in Malaysia. <i>Journal of Education for Teaching, 38</i> (3), 295–307.
81	Gamiz-Sanchez, Gallego-Arrufat & Crisol-Moya	2016	Impact of Electronic Portfolios on Prospective Teachers' Participation, Motivation, and Autonomous Learning	Journal of Information Technology Education-Research	Gamiz-Sanchez, V. M., Gallego-Arrufat, M. J., & Crisol-Moya, E. (2016). Impact of Electronic Portfolios on Prospective Teachers' Participation, Motivation, and Autonomous Learning. <i>Journal of Information Technology Education-Research, 15</i> , 517–533.
82	Gencil	2017	The Effect of Portfolio Assessments on Metacognitive Skills and on Attitudes toward a Course	Educational Sciences	Gencil, I. E. (2017). The Effect of Portfolio Assessments on Metacognitive Skills and on Attitudes toward a Course. <i>Educational Sciences, 17</i> (1), 293–319.
83	Gitomer, Martinez, Battey & Hyland	2021	Assessing the Assessment: Evidence of Reliability and Validity in the edTPA	American Educational Research Journal	Gitomer, D. H., Martinez, J. F., Battey, D., & Hyland, N. E. (2021). Assessing the Assessment: Evidence of Reliability and Validity in the edTPA. <i>American Educational Research Journal, 58</i> (1), 3–31.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
84	Gomez-Gomez	2021	Teacher education in the face of new virtual teaching and learning opportunities from a technological, pedagogical and human perspective	Revista Publicaciones	Gomez-Gomez, M. (2021). Teacher education in the face of new virtual teaching and learning opportunities from a technological, pedagogical and human perspective. <i>Revista Publicaciones</i> , 51(3), 585–603.
85	Goodchild, Apkarian, Rasmussen & Katz	2021	Critical stance within a community of inquiry in an advanced mathematics course for pre-service teachers	Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education	Goodchild, S., Apkarian, N., Rasmussen, C., & Katz, B. (2021). Critical stance within a community of inquiry in an advanced mathematics course for pre-service teachers. <i>Journal of Mathematics Teacher Education</i> , 24(3), 231–252.
86	Granberg	2010	E-Portfolios in Teacher Education 2002–2009: The Social Construction of Discourse, Design and Dissemination	European Journal of Teacher Education	Granberg, C. (2010). E-Portfolios in Teacher Education 2002–2009: The Social Construction of Discourse, Design and Dissemination. <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 33(3), 309–322.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
87	Groom & Maunonen-Eskelinen	2006	The Use of Portfolios to Develop Reflective Practice in Teacher Training: A Comparative and Collaborative Approach between Two Teacher Training Providers in the UK and Finland	Teaching in Higher Education	Groom, B., & Maunonen-Eskelinen, I. (2006). The Use of Portfolios to Develop Reflective Practice in Teacher Training: A Comparative and Collaborative Approach between Two Teacher Training Providers in the UK and Finland. <i>Teaching in Higher Education</i> , 11(3), 291–300.
88	Gujarati	2019	Reflecting on Action: Implications from the Child Mathematics Inquiry Portfolio	Journal of Mathematics Education	Gujarati, J. (2019). Reflecting on Action: Implications from the Child Mathematics Inquiry Portfolio. <i>Journal of Mathematics Education</i> , 10(1), 1–10.
89	Hagerman & Coleman	2017	Implementing a Digital Hub Strategy: Preservice Teacher and Faculty Perspectives	LEARNing Landscapes	Hagerman, M. S., & Coleman, J. (2017). Implementing a Digital Hub Strategy: Preservice Teacher and Faculty Perspectives. <i>LEARNing Landscapes</i> , 11(1), 137–151.
90	Hall & Townsend	2017	Using critical incidents and E-Portfolios to understand the emergent practice of Japanese student-teachers of English	Teaching and Teacher Education	Hall, J. M., & Townsend, S. D. C. (2017). Using critical incidents and E-Portfolios to understand the emergent practice of Japanese student-teachers of English. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 62, 1–9.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
91	Handel, Wimmer & Ziegler	2020	E-portfolio use and its effects on exam performance - a field study	Studies in Higher Education	Handel, M., Wimmer, B., & Ziegler, A. (2020). E-portfolio use and its effects on exam performance - a field study. <i>Studies in Higher Education</i> , 45(2), 258–270.
92	Harland	2005	Developing a Portfolio to Promote Authentic Enquiry in Teacher Education	Teaching in Higher Education	Harland, T. (2005). Developing a Portfolio to Promote Authentic Enquiry in Teacher Education. <i>Teaching in Higher Education</i> , 10(3), 327–337.
93	Hartmann & Calandra	2007	Diffusion and Reinvention of ePortfolio Design Practices as a Catalyst for Teacher Learning	Technology, Pedagogy and Education	Hartmann, C., & Calandra, B. (2007). Diffusion and Reinvention of ePortfolio Design Practices as a Catalyst for Teacher Learning. <i>Technology, Pedagogy and Education</i> , 16(1), 77–93.
94	Hartwick & Mason	2014	Using Introductory Videos to Enhance ePortfolios and to Make Them Useful in the Hiring Process	International Journal of ePortfolio	Hartwick, J. M. M., & Mason, R. W. (2014). Using Introductory Videos to Enhance ePortfolios and to Make Them Useful in the Hiring Process. <i>International Journal of ePortfolio</i> , 4(2), 169–184.
95	Hauge, T.	2006	Portfolios and ICT as Means of Professional Learning in Teacher Education	Studies in Educational Evaluation	Hauge, T. E. (2006). Portfolios and ICT as Means of Professional Learning in Teacher Education. <i>Studies in Educational Evaluation</i> , 32(1), 23–36.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
96	Henry, Campbell, Thompson, Patriarca, Luterbach, Lys & Covington	2013	The Predictive Validity of Measures of Teacher Candidate Programs and Performance: Toward an Evidence-Based Approach to Teacher Preparation	Journal of Teacher Education	Henry, G. T., Campbell, S. L., Thompson, C. L., Patriarca, L. A., Luterbach, K. J., Lys, D. B., & Covington, V. M. (2013). The Predictive Validity of Measures of Teacher Candidate Programs and Performance: Toward an Evidence-Based Approach to Teacher Preparation. <i>Journal of Teacher Education, 64</i> (5), 439–453.
97	Herner-Patnode & Lee	2009	A Capstone Experience for Preservice Teachers: Building a Web-Based Portfolio	Educational Technology & Society	Herner-Patnode, L. M., & Lee, H.-J. (2009). A Capstone Experience for Preservice Teachers: Building a Web-Based Portfolio. <i>Educational Technology & Society, 12</i> (2), 101–110.
98	Highfield, De Gioia & Lane	2016	Tablet technology and cloud storage as evidence of pedagogic development in pre-service teacher education	Australasian Journal of Early Childhood	Highfield, K., De Gioia, K., & Lane, R. (2016). Tablet technology and cloud storage as evidence of pedagogic development in pre-service teacher education. <i>Australasian Journal of Early Childhood, 41</i> (4), 44–51.
99	Hildebrandt & Swanson	2019	The control, content, and consequences of edTPA: World language teacher educators' perceptions	Foreign Language Annals	Hildebrandt, S. A., & Swanson, P. (2019). The control, content, and consequences of edTPA: World language teacher educators' perceptions. <i>Foreign Language Annals, 52</i> (3), 670–686.

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100	Holden, Parkes & O'Leary	2020	Teacher candidate perceptions of the edTPA in physical and health education	Curriculum Studies in Health and Physical Education	Holden, S. L., Parkes, C., & O'Leary, N. (2020). Teacher candidate perceptions of the edTPA in physical and health education. <i>Curriculum Studies in Health and Physical Education</i> , 11(3), 237–251.
101	Hopper, Fu, Sanford & Monk	2018	What Is a Digital Electronic Portfolio in Teacher Education? A Case Study of Instructors' and Students' Enabling Insights on the Electronic Portfolio Process	Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology	Hopper, T., Fu, H., Sanford, K., & Monk, D. (2018). What Is a Digital Electronic Portfolio in Teacher Education? A Case Study of Instructors' and Students' Enabling Insights on the Electronic Portfolio Process. <i>Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology</i> , 44(2). 1–20.
102	Hopper, Sanford & Bonsor-Kurki	2012	Stitching Together a Teacher's Body of Knowledge: Frankie N. Stein's ePortfolio	E-Learning and Digital Media	Hopper, T., Sanford, K., & Bonsor-Kurki, S. (2012). Stitching Together a Teacher's Body of Knowledge: Frankie N. Stein's ePortfolio. <i>E-Learning and Digital Media</i> , 9(1), 29–42.
103	Houston	2016	Do Scaffolding Tools Improve Reflective Writing in Professional Portfolios? A Content Analysis of Reflective Writing in an Advanced Preparation Program	Action in Teacher Education	Houston, C. R. (2016). Do Scaffolding Tools Improve Reflective Writing in Professional Portfolios? A Content Analysis of Reflective Writing in an Advanced Preparation Program. <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 38(4), 399–409.

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104	Hung	2012	A Washback Study on E-Portfolio Assessment in an English as a Foreign Language Teacher Preparation Program	Computer Assisted Language Learning	Hung, S.-T. A. (2012). A Washback Study on E-Portfolio Assessment in an English as a Foreign Language Teacher Preparation Program. <i>Computer Assisted Language Learning</i> , 25(1), 21–36.
105	Imhof & Picard	2009	Views on Using Portfolio in Teacher Education	Teaching and Teacher Education	Imhof, M., & Picard, C. (2009). Views on Using Portfolio in Teacher Education. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 25(1), 149–154.
106	Jeldres & Espinoza	2019	Chilean Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions Towards Benefits and Challenges of EFL Writing Portfolios	Profile-Issues in Teachers Professional Development	Jeldres, P. A. S., & Espinoza, M. C. (2019). Chilean Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions Towards Benefits and Challenges of EFL Writing Portfolios. <i>Profile-Issues in Teachers Professional Development</i> , 21(2), 79–96.
107	Johnson-Leslie	2009	Comparing the Efficacy of an Engineered-Based System (College Livetext) with an Off-the-Shelf General Tool (Hyperstudio) for Developing Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education	Journal of Educational Technology Systems	Johnson-Leslie, N. A. (2009). Comparing the Efficacy of an Engineered-Based System (College Livetext) with an Off-the-Shelf General Tool (Hyperstudio) for Developing Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education. <i>Journal of Educational Technology Systems</i> , 37(4), 385–404.
108	Jones	2010	A Professional Practice Portfolio for Quality Learning	Higher Education Quarterly	Jones, E. (2010). A Professional Practice Portfolio for Quality Learning. <i>Higher Education Quarterly</i> , 64(3), 292–312.

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109	Kaasila & Lauriala	2012	How Do Pre-Service Teachers' Reflective Processes Differ in Relation to Different Contexts?	European Journal of Teacher Education	Kaasila, R., & Lauriala, A. (2012). How Do Pre-Service Teachers' Reflective Processes Differ in Relation to Different Contexts? <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 35(1), 77–89.
110	Kabilan	2016	Using Facebook as an E-Portfolio in Enhancing Pre-Service Teachers' Professional Development	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Kabilan, M. K. (2016). Using Facebook as an E-Portfolio in Enhancing Pre-Service Teachers' Professional Development. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 32(1), 19–31.
111	Kabilan & Khan	2012	Assessing Pre-Service English Language Teachers' Learning Using E-Portfolios: Benefits, Challenges and Competencies Gained	Computers & Education	Kabilan, M. K., & Khan, M. A. (2012). Assessing Pre-Service English Language Teachers' Learning Using E-Portfolios: Benefits, Challenges and Competencies Gained. <i>Computers & Education</i> , 58(4), 1007–1020.
112	Karsak	2016	The Two Faces of Teacher Candidates' Portfolio Experiences: Tradition and Facebook	Universal Journal of Educational Research	Karsak, H. G. O. (2016). The Two Faces of Teacher Candidates' Portfolio Experiences: Tradition and Facebook. <i>Universal Journal of Educational Research</i> , 4, 216–225.

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113	Kecik, Aydin, Sakar, Dikdere, Aydin, Yuksel & Caner	2012	Determining the Feasibility of an E-Portfolio Application in a Distance Education Teaching Practice Course	International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning	Kecik, I., Aydin, B., Sakar, N., Dikdere, M., Aydin, S., Yuksel, I., & Caner, M. (2012). Determining the Feasibility of an E-Portfolio Application in a Distance Education Teaching Practice Course. <i>International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning</i> , 13(2), 160–180.
114	Kelly & Hancock	2018	Alberta School Principals' Use of Professional Portfolios in Teacher Hiring	Canadian Journal of Education	Kelly, D., & Hancock, S. (2018). Alberta School Principals' Use of Professional Portfolios in Teacher Hiring. <i>Canadian Journal of Education</i> , 41(4), 1050–1078.
115	Kertesz	2016	Three Key Conditions to Revitalise an ePortfolio Program in Response to Increasing Regulation of Teacher Education	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Kertesz, J. L. (2016). Three Key Conditions to Revitalise an ePortfolio Program in Response to Increasing Regulation of Teacher Education. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 41(8), 102–117.
116	Kessler	2021	Performative enactments of teacher evaluation: Two preservice teachers and the edTPA	Policy Futures in Education	Kessler, M. A. (2021). Performative enactments of teacher evaluation: Two preservice teachers and the edTPA. <i>Policy Futures in Education</i> , 19(1), 44–62.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
117	Kessler, Jones & Johnston-Parsons	2020	Who Is Watching? What Do They Want? A Foucauldian Analysis of Teacher Candidates' Experiences With the edTPA	Teachers College Record	Kessler, M. A., Jones, A., & Johnston-Parsons, M. (2020). Who Is Watching? What Do They Want? A Foucauldian Analysis of Teacher Candidates' Experiences With the edTPA. <i>Teachers College Record</i> , 122(12), 1–36.
118	Khales	2016	Using Electronic Portfolio to Promote Professional Learning Community for Pre-Service Early Childhood Teachers at Alquds University	Journal of Education and Practice	Khales, B. (2016). Using Electronic Portfolio to Promote Professional Learning Community for Pre-Service Early Childhood Teachers at Alquds University. <i>Journal of Education and Practice</i> , 7(26), 127–136.
119	Kirchner, Evans & Norman	2010	Examining the Relationship between Two Assessments of Teacher Effectiveness	Action in Teacher Education	Kirchner, J., Evans, C. S., & Norman, A. D. (2010). Examining the Relationship between Two Assessments of Teacher Effectiveness. <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 32(1), 73–81.
120	Kitchenham	2008	E-Portfolios in Teacher Education: The UNBC Experience	Collected Essays on Learning and Teaching	Kitchenham, A. (2008). E-Portfolios in Teacher Education: The UNBC Experience. <i>Collected Essays on Learning and Teaching</i> , 1, 138–144.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
121	Klampfer, & Kohler	2015	Learners' and teachers' motivation toward using e-portfolios. An empirical investigation	International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life-Long Learning	Klampfer, A., & Kohler, T. (2015). Learners' and teachers' motivation toward using e-portfolios. An empirical investigation. <i>International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life-Long Learning</i> , 25(2), 189–207.
122	Kleyn, Lopez & Makar	2015	What About Bilingualism? A Critical Reflection on the edTPA With Teachers of Emergent Bilinguals	Bilingual Research Journal	Kleyn, T., Lopez, D., & Makar, C. (2015). What About Bilingualism? A Critical Reflection on the edTPA With Teachers of Emergent Bilinguals. <i>Bilingual Research Journal</i> , 38(1), 88–106.
123	Kocoglu	2008	Turkish EFL Student Teachers' Perceptions on the Role of Electronic Portfolios in Their Professional Development	Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	Kocoglu, Z. (2008). Turkish EFL Student Teachers' Perceptions on the Role of Electronic Portfolios in Their Professional Development. <i>Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 7(3), 71–79.

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124	Koehler, Greenhalgh, Rosenberg & Keenan	2017	What the Tech Is Going on with Teachers' Digital Teaching Portfolios? Using the TPACK Framework to Analyze Teachers' Technological Understanding	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Koehler, M., Greenhalgh, S., Rosenberg, J., & Keenan, S. (2017). What the Tech Is Going on with Teachers' Digital Teaching Portfolios? Using the TPACK Framework to Analyze Teachers' Technological Understanding. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 25(1), 31–59.
125	Körkkö, Kyrö-Ämmälä & Turunen	2016	Professional Development through Reflection in Teacher Education	Teaching and Teacher Education	Körkkö, M., Kyrö-Ämmälä, O., & Turunen, T. (2016). Professional Development through Reflection in Teacher Education. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 55, 198–206.
126	Kremzer	2021	Academic reflective writing or anecdotal storytelling: a study on pre-service EFL teaching portfolios	European Journal of Teacher Education	Kremzer, V. (2021). Academic reflective writing or anecdotal storytelling: a study on pre-service EFL teaching portfolios. <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> . 1–25.
127	Lambe, McNair & Smith	2013	Special Educational Needs, e-Learning and the Reflective e-Portfolio: Implications for Developing and Assessing Competence in Pre-Service Education	Journal of Education for Teaching	Lambe, J., McNair, V., & Smith, R. (2013). Special Educational Needs, e-Learning and the Reflective e-Portfolio: Implications for Developing and Assessing Competence in Pre-Service Education. <i>Journal of Education for Teaching</i> , 39(2), 181–196.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
128	Lewis	2017	ePortfolio as Pedagogy: Threshold Concepts for Curriculum Design	E-Learning and Digital Media	Lewis, L. (2017). ePortfolio as Pedagogy: Threshold Concepts for Curriculum Design. <i>E-Learning and Digital Media</i> , 14, 72–85.
129	Lin	2008	Preservice teachers' learning experiences of constructing e-portfolios online	Internet and Higher Education	Lin, Q. Y. (2008). Preservice teachers' learning experiences of constructing e-portfolios online. <i>Internet and Higher Education</i> , 11(3-4), 194–200.
130	Lind	2007	e-Portfolios in Music Teacher Education	Innovate: Journal of Online Education	Lind, V. (2007). e-Portfolios in Music Teacher Education. <i>Innovate: Journal of Online Education</i> , 3(3). 1–7.
131	Ma & Rada	2006	Individual Effects of a Web-Based Accountability System in a Teacher Education Program	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Ma, X., & Rada, R. (2006). Individual Effects of a Web-Based Accountability System in a Teacher Education Program. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 22(3), 111–119.
132	Maher & Gerbic	2009	E-Portfolios as a Pedagogical Device in Primary Teacher Education: The AUT University Experience	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Maher, M., & Gerbic, P. (2009). E-Portfolios as a Pedagogical Device in Primary Teacher Education: The AUT University Experience. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 34(5), 43–53.

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133	Makokotlela	2020	An E-Portfolio as an Assessment Strategy in an Open Distance Learning Context	International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education	Makokotlela, M. V. (2020). An E-Portfolio as an Assessment Strategy in an Open Distance Learning Context. <i>International Journal of Information and Communication Technology Education</i> , 16(4), 122–134.
134	Mamvuto & Kangai	2021	Portfolio implementation for self-reflection and professional growth of students in the arts	Visual Studies	Mamvuto, A., & Kangai, P. (2021). Portfolio implementation for self-reflection and professional growth of students in the arts. <i>Visual Studies</i> . 1–9.
135	Manoban	2021	Project-Based Learning and E-Portfolios for Preservice Teachers in Japanese Language Education	Journal of Education and Learning	Manoban, A. (2021). Project-Based Learning and E-Portfolios for Preservice Teachers in Japanese Language Education. <i>Journal of Education and Learning</i> , 10(4), 40–50.
136	Mansvelder-Longayroux, Beijaard & Verloop	2007	The Portfolio as a Tool for Stimulating Reflection by Student Teachers	Teaching and Teacher Education	Mansvelder-Longayroux, D. D., Beijaard, D., & Verloop, N. (2007). The Portfolio as a Tool for Stimulating Reflection by Student Teachers. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 23(1), 47–62.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
137	Mansvelder-Longayroux, Beijaard, Verloop & Vermunt	2007	Functions of the Learning Portfolio in Student Teachers' Learning Process	Teachers College Record	Mansvelder-Longayroux, D. D., Beijaard, D., Verloop, N., & Vermunt, J. D. (2007). Functions of the Learning Portfolio in Student Teachers' Learning Process. <i>Teachers College Record</i> , 109(1), 126–159.
138	Margolis & Doring	2013	National Assessments for Student Teachers: Documenting Teaching Readiness to the Tipping Point	Action in Teacher Education	Margolis, J., & Doring, A. (2013). National Assessments for Student Teachers: Documenting Teaching Readiness to the Tipping Point. <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 35(4), 272–285.
139	Masters	2013	Scaffolding Pre-Service Teachers Representing Their Learning Journeys with ePortfolios	Journal of Learning Design	Masters, J. (2013). Scaffolding Pre-Service Teachers Representing Their Learning Journeys with ePortfolios. <i>Journal of Learning Design</i> , 6(1), 1–9.
140	McIntyre & Dangel	2009	Teacher Candidate Portfolios: Routine or Reflective Action?	Action in Teacher Education	McIntyre, C., & Dangel, J. R. (2009). Teacher Candidate Portfolios: Routine or Reflective Action? <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 31(2), 74–85.
141	McWhorter, Delello, Roberts, Raisor & Fowler	2013	A Cross-Case Analysis of the Use of Web-Based ePortfolios in Higher Education	Journal of Information Technology Education	McWhorter, R. R., Delello, J. A., Roberts, P. B., Raisor, C. M., & Fowler, D. A. (2013). A Cross-Case Analysis of the Use of Web-Based ePortfolios in Higher Education. <i>Journal of Information Technology Education</i> 12, 253–286.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
142	Meeus, Van Petegem & Meijer	2008	Stimulating Independent Learning: A Quasi-Experimental Study on Portfolio	Educational Studies	Meeus, W., Van Petegem, P., & Meijer, J. (2008). Stimulating Independent Learning: A Quasi-Experimental Study on Portfolio. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 34(5), 469–481.
143	Meeus, Van Petegem & Meijer	2008	Portfolio as a Means of Promoting Autonomous Learning in Teacher Education: A Quasi-Experimental Study	Educational Research	Meeus, W., Van Petegem, P., & Meijer, J. (2008). Portfolio as a Means of Promoting Autonomous Learning in Teacher Education: A Quasi-Experimental Study. <i>Educational Research</i> , 50(4), 361–386.
144	Meyer & Latham	2008	Implementing Electronic Portfolios: Benefits, Challenges, and Suggestions	EDUCAUSE Quarterly	Meyer, B., & Latham, N. (2008). Implementing Electronic Portfolios: Benefits, Challenges, and Suggestions. <i>EDUCAUSE Quarterly</i> , 31(1), 34-41.
145	Milman	2005	Web-Based Digital Teaching Portfolios: Fostering Reflection and Technology Competence in Preservice Teacher Education Students	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Milman, N. B. (2005). Web-Based Digital Teaching Portfolios: Fostering Reflection and Technology Competence in Preservice Teacher Education Students. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 13(3), 373–396.

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146	Mirici & Hergüner	2015	A Digital European Self-Assessment Tool for Student Teachers of Foreign Languages: The EPOSTL	Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	Mirici, I. H., & Hergüner, S. (2015). A Digital European Self-Assessment Tool for Student Teachers of Foreign Languages: The EPOSTL. <i>Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 14(1), 1–10.
147	Mok	2012	As a Student, I Do Think that the Learning Effectiveness of Electronic Portfolios Depends, to Quite a Large Extent, on the Attitude of Students!	Electronic Journal of e-Learning	Mok, J. (2012). "As a Student, I Do Think that the Learning Effectiveness of Electronic Portfolios Depends, to Quite a Large Extent, on the Attitude of Students!". <i>Electronic Journal of e-Learning</i> , 10(4), 407–416.
148	Moran, Vozzo, Reid, Pietsch & Hatton	2013	How Can Technology Make This Work? Preservice Teachers, Off-Campus	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Moran, W., Vozzo, L., Reid, J.-A., Pietsch, M., & Hatton, C. (2013). How Can Technology Make This Work? Preservice Teachers, Off-Campus. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 38(5). 116–130.
149	Morrison, Masters & Quentin-Baxter	2018	Implementation of Portfolios within Australian Initial Teacher Education: Who's Leading the Charge?	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Morrison, C., Masters, J., & Quentin-Baxter, M. (2018). Implementation of Portfolios within Australian Initial Teacher Education: Who's Leading the Charge? <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 43(7), 98–109.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
150	Mosely	2005	The Value of Professional Teaching Portfolios to Prospective Employers: School Administrators' Views	Professional Educator	Mosely, C. (2005). The Value of Professional Teaching Portfolios to Prospective Employers: School Administrators' Views. <i>Professional Educator</i> , 27, 58–72.
151	Munandar, Maryani, Rohmat & Ruhimat	2020	Establishing the Profesionalism of Geography Teacher through Authentic Assessment Field Study	International Journal of Instruction	Munandar, A., Maryani, E., Rohmat, D., & Ruhimat, M. (2020). Establishing the Profesionalism of Geography Teacher through Authentic Assessment Field Study. <i>International Journal of Instruction</i> , 13(2), 797–818.
152	Nagle	2009	Becoming a Reflective Practitioner in the Age of Accountability	Educational Forum	Nagle, J. F. (2009). Becoming a Reflective Practitioner in the Age of Accountability. <i>Educational Forum</i> , 73(1), 76–86.
153	Namaziandost, Alekasir, Sawalmeh & Miftah	2020	Investigating the Iranian EFL learners' attitudes towards the implementation of e-portfolios in English learning and assessment	Cogent Education	Namaziandost, E., Alekasir, S., Sawalmeh, M. H. M., & Miftah, M. Z. (2020). Investigating the Iranian EFL learners' attitudes towards the implementation of e-portfolios in English learning and assessment. <i>Cogent Education</i> , 7(1). 1–32.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
154	Ndoye, Ritzhaupt & Parker	2012	Use of ePortfolios in K-12 Teacher Hiring in North Carolina: Perspectives of School Principals	International Journal of Education Policy and Leadership	Ndoye, A., Ritzhaupt, A. D., & Parker, M. A. (2012). Use of ePortfolios in K-12 Teacher Hiring in North Carolina: Perspectives of School Principals. <i>International Journal of Education Policy and Leadership</i> , 7(4), 1–10.
155	Ntuli, Keengwe, & Kyei-Blankson	2009	Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: A Case Study of Early Childhood Teacher Candidates	Early Childhood Education Journal	Ntuli, E., Keengwe, J., & Kyei-Blankson, L. (2009). Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: A Case Study of Early Childhood Teacher Candidates. <i>Early Childhood Education Journal</i> , 37(2), 121–126.
156	Oakley, Pegrum & Johnston	2014	Introducing E-Portfolios to Pre-Service Teachers as Tools for Reflection and Growth: Lessons Learnt	Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education	Oakley, G., Pegrum, M., & Johnston, S. (2014). Introducing E-Portfolios to Pre-Service Teachers as Tools for Reflection and Growth: Lessons Learnt. <i>Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 42(1), 36–50.
157	Ogan-Bekiroglu	2014	Quality of Preservice Physics Teachers' Reflections in Their Teaching Portfolios and Their Perceived Reflections: Do They Intersect?	Action in Teacher Education	Ogan-Bekiroglu, F. (2014). Quality of Preservice Physics Teachers' Reflections in Their Teaching Portfolios and Their Perceived Reflections: Do They Intersect? <i>Action in Teacher Education</i> , 36(2), 157–170.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
158	Oner & Adadan	2011	Use of Web-Based Portfolios as Tools for Reflection in Preservice Teacher Education	Journal of Teacher Education	Oner, D., & Adadan, E. (2011). Use of Web-Based Portfolios as Tools for Reflection in Preservice Teacher Education. <i>Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 62(5), 477–492.
159	Oner & Adadan	2016	Are Integrated Portfolio Systems the Answer? An Evaluation of a Web-Based Portfolio System to Improve Preservice Teachers' Reflective Thinking Skills	Journal of Computing in Higher Education	Oner, D., & Adadan, E. (2016). Are Integrated Portfolio Systems the Answer? An Evaluation of a Web-Based Portfolio System to Improve Preservice Teachers' Reflective Thinking Skills. <i>Journal of Computing in Higher Education</i> , 28(2), 236–260.
160	Ozdemir & Erdemci	2017	The Effect of Mobile Portfolio (M-Portfolio) Supported Mastery Learning Model on Students' Achievement and their Attitudes towards Using Internet	Journal of Education and Training Studies	Ozdemir, O., & Erdemci, H. (2017). The Effect of Mobile Portfolio (M-Portfolio) Supported Mastery Learning Model on Students' Achievement and their Attitudes towards Using Internet. <i>Journal of Education and Training Studies</i> , 5(3), 62–70.
161	Painter & Wetzel	2005	School Administrators' Perceptions of the Use of Electronic Portfolios in K-8 Teacher Hiring	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Painter, S., & Wetzel, K. (2005). School Administrators' Perceptions of the Use of Electronic Portfolios in K-8 Teacher Hiring. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 22(1), 23–29.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
162	Parker, Ndoye & Ritzhaupt	2012	Qualitative Analysis of Student Perceptions of E-Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program	Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education	Parker, M., Ndoye, A., & Ritzhaupt, A. D. (2012). Qualitative Analysis of Student Perceptions of E-Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program. <i>Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education</i> , 28(3), 99–107.
163	Paugh, Wendell, Power & Gilbert	2018	'It's Not That Easy to Solve': edTPA and Preservice Teacher Learning	Teaching Education	Paugh, P., Wendell, K. B., Power, C., & Gilbert, M. (2018). 'It's Not That Easy to Solve': edTPA and Preservice Teacher Learning. <i>Teaching Education</i> , 29(2), 147–164.
164	Payne & Burrack	2017	Predictive Ability from ePortfolios of Student Achievement Associated with Professional Teaching Standards: An Exploratory Case Study	Research and Issues in Music Education	Payne, P., & Burrack, F. (2017). Predictive Ability from ePortfolios of Student Achievement Associated with Professional Teaching Standards: An Exploratory Case Study. <i>Research and Issues in Music Education</i> , 13(1). 1–23.
165	Pellerin	2018	The Integration of ePortfolios in Higher Education, and Students' Perceptions	Journal of Interactive Learning Research	Pellerin, M. (2018). The Integration of ePortfolios in Higher Education, and Students' Perceptions. <i>Journal of Interactive Learning Research</i> , 29(4), 529–544.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
166	Pelliccione & Raison	2009	Promoting the Scholarship of Teaching through Reflective E-Portfolios in Teacher Education	Journal of Education for Teaching	Pelliccione, L., & Raison, G. (2009). Promoting the Scholarship of Teaching through Reflective E-Portfolios in Teacher Education. <i>Journal of Education for Teaching</i> , 35(3), 271–281.
167	Penny & Kinslow	2006	Faculty Perceptions of Electronic Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program	Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education	Penny, C., & Kinslow, J. (2006). Faculty Perceptions of Electronic Portfolios in a Teacher Education Program. <i>Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 6(4), 418–435.
168	Plaisir, Hachey & Theilheimer	2011	Their Portfolios, Our Role: Examining a Community College Teacher Education Digital Portfolio Program from the Students' Perspective	Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education	Plaisir, J. Y., Hachey, A. C., & Theilheimer, R. (2011). Their Portfolios, Our Role: Examining a Community College Teacher Education Digital Portfolio Program from the Students' Perspective. <i>Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education</i> , 32(2), 159–175.
169	Reynolds & Park	2021	Examining the relationship between the Educative Teacher Performance Assessment and preservice teachers' pedagogical content knowledge	Journal of Research in Science Teaching	Reynolds, W. M., & Park, S. (2021). Examining the relationship between the Educative Teacher Performance Assessment and preservice teachers' pedagogical content knowledge. <i>Journal of Research in Science Teaching</i> , 58(5), 721–748.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
170	Rifa-Valls, Dominguez, Cervello & Barquilla	2011	Experimenting with Visual Storytelling in Students' Portfolios: Narratives of Visual Pedagogy for Pre-Service Teacher Education	International Journal of Art & Design Education	Rifa-Valls, M., Dominguez, T. T., Cervello, E. G., & Barquilla, S. P. (2011). Experimenting with Visual Storytelling in Students' Portfolios: Narratives of Visual Pedagogy for Pre- Service Teacher Education. <i>International Journal of Art & Design Education, 30(2),</i> 293–306.
171	Rigoni, Pugach, Longwell- Grice & Ford	2013	A Programmatic View of Portfolios for Urban Teacher Preparation: A Second Look	Education and Urban Society	Rigoni, K. K., Pugach, M. C., Longwell- Grice, H., & Ford, A. (2013). A Programmatic View of Portfolios for Urban Teacher Preparation: A Second Look. <i>Education and Urban Society, 45(1),</i> 88–119.
172	Ritzhaupt, Ndoye & Parker	2010	Validation of the Electronic Portfolio Student Perspective Instrument (EPSPI): Conditions under a Different Integration Initiative	Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education	Ritzhaupt, A. D., Ndoye, A., & Parker, M. A. (2010). Validation of the Electronic Portfolio Student Perspective Instrument (EPSPI): Conditions under a Different Integration Initiative. <i>Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education,</i> 26(3), 111–119.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
173	Ritzhaupt, Singh, Seyferth & Dedrick	2008	Development of the Electronic Portfolio Student Perspective Instrument: An ePortfolio Integration Initiative	Journal of Computing in Higher Education	Ritzhaupt, A. D., Singh, O., Seyferth, T., & Dedrick, R. F. (2008). Development of the Electronic Portfolio Student Perspective Instrument: An ePortfolio Integration Initiative. <i>Journal of Computing in Higher Education</i> , 19(2), 47–71.
174	Roberts	2018	Developing reflection through an ePortfolio-based learning environment: design principles for further implementation	Technology Pedagogy and Education	Roberts, P. (2018). Developing reflection through an ePortfolio-based learning environment: design principles for further implementation. <i>Technology Pedagogy and Education</i> , 27(3), 313–326.
175	Roberts & Kirk	2019	Introducing an ePortfolio into Practicum-Based Units: Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of Effective Support	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Roberts, P., & Kirk, G. (2019). Introducing an ePortfolio into Practicum-Based Units: Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of Effective Support. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 44(5), 79–93.
176	Russell & Davidson Devall	2016	An Examination of the EeTPA Portfolio Assessment and Other Measures of Teacher Preparation and Readiness	Foreign Language Annals	Russell, V., & Davidson Devall, K. F. (2016). An Examination of the EeTPA Portfolio Assessment and Other Measures of Teacher Preparation and Readiness. <i>Foreign Language Annals</i> , 49(3), 479–501.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
177	Saavedra Jeldres & Campos Espinoza	2019	Chilean Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions towards Benefits and Challenges of EFL Writing Portfolios	PROFILE: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development	Saavedra Jeldres, P. A., & Campos Espinoza, M. (2019). Chilean Pre-Service Teachers' Perceptions towards Benefits and Challenges of EFL Writing Portfolios. <i>PROFILE: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development</i> , 21(1), 79–96.
178	San Jose	2017	Evaluating, Comparing, and Best Practice in Electronic Portfolio System Use	Journal of Educational Technology Systems	San Jose, D. L. (2017). Evaluating, Comparing, and Best Practice in Electronic Portfolio System Use. <i>Journal of Educational Technology Systems</i> , 45(4), 476–498.
179	Sardegna & Dugartsyrenova	2014	Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers' Perspectives on Learning With Technology	Foreign Language Annals	Sardegna, V. G., & Dugartsyrenova, V. A. (2014). Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers' Perspectives on Learning With Technology. <i>Foreign Language Annals</i> , 47(1), 147–167.
180	Savage	2016	Mapping pre-service teachers' evolving information and communication technologies pedagogy	Technology Pedagogy and Education	Savage, M. (2016). Mapping pre-service teachers' evolving information and communication technologies pedagogy. <i>Technology Pedagogy and Education</i> , 25(5), 533–554.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
181	Segers, Gijbels & Thurlings	2008	The relationship between students' perceptions of portfolio assessment practice and their approaches to learning	Educational Studies	Segers, M., Gijbels, D., & Thurlings, M. (2008). The relationship between students' perceptions of portfolio assessment practice and their approaches to learning. <i>Educational Studies</i> , 34(1), 35–44.
182	Sevim	2012	Portfolio applications in science teaching	Energy Education Science and Technology	Sevim, S. (2012). Portfolio applications in science teaching. <i>Energy Education Science and Technology</i> , 4(2), 687–694.
183	Shepherd & Hannafin	2009	Beyond Recollection: Reexamining Preservice Teacher Practices Using Structured Evidence, Analysis, and Reflection	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Shepherd, C., & Hannafin, M. (2009). Beyond Recollection: Reexamining Preservice Teacher Practices Using Structured Evidence, Analysis, and Reflection. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 17(2). 1–23.
184	Shepherd & Hannafin	2011	Supporting Preservice Teacher Inquiry with Electronic Portfolios	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Shepherd, C., & Hannafin, M. (2011). Supporting Preservice Teacher Inquiry with Electronic Portfolios. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 19(2), 189–207.
185	Shepherd & Hannafin	2008	Examining Preservice Teacher Inquiry through Video-Based, Formative Assessment e-Portfolios	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Shepherd, C. E., & Hannafin, M. J. (2008). Examining Preservice Teacher Inquiry through Video-Based, Formative Assessment e-Portfolios. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 25(1), 31–37.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
186	Sherfinski, Hayes, Zhang & Jalalifard	2019	Do It All but Don't Kill Us: (Re)positioning Teacher Educators and Preservice Teachers amidst edTPA and the Teacher Strike in West Virginia	Education policy analysis archives	Sherfinski, M., Hayes, S., Zhang, J., & Jalalifard, M. (2019). "Do It All but Don't Kill Us": (Re)positioning Teacher Educators and Preservice Teachers amidst edTPA and the Teacher Strike in West Virginia. <i>Education policy analysis archives</i> , 27(151). 1–45.
187	Sherfinski, Jalalifard, Zhang & Hayes	2019	Narrative Portfolios as Culturally Responsive Resistance to Neoliberal Early Childhood Teacher Education: A Case Study	Journal of Research in Childhood Education	Sherfinski, M., Jalalifard, M., Zhang, J., & Hayes, S. (2019). Narrative Portfolios as Culturally Responsive Resistance to Neoliberal Early Childhood Teacher Education: A Case Study. <i>Journal of Research in Childhood Education</i> , 33(3), 490–519.
188	Shroff, Deneen & Ng	2011	Analysis of the Technology Acceptance Model in Examining Students' Behavioural Intention to Use an e-Portfolio System	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Shroff, R. H., Deneen, C. C., & Ng, E. M. W. (2011). Analysis of the Technology Acceptance Model in Examining Students' Behavioural Intention to Use an e-Portfolio System. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 27(4), 600–618.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
189	Silveira, Beaugard & Bull	2017	Development of the Processfolio: Promoting Preservice Music Teacher Reflection Through Authentic Assessment	Journal of Music Teacher Education	Silveira, J. M., Beaugard, J., & Bull, T. (2017). Development of the Processfolio: Promoting Preservice Music Teacher Reflection Through Authentic Assessment. <i>Journal of Music Teacher Education</i> , 27(1), 11–23.
190	Slepcevic-Zach & Stock	2018	ePortfolio as a tool for reflection and self-reflection	Reflective Practice	Slepcevic-Zach, P., & Stock, M. (2018). ePortfolio as a tool for reflection and self-reflection. <i>Reflective Practice</i> , 19(3), 291–307.
191	Smith & Tillema	2007	Use of Criteria in Assessing Teaching Portfolios: Judgemental Practices in Summative Evaluation	Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research	Smith, K., & Tillema, H. (2007). Use of Criteria in Assessing Teaching Portfolios: Judgemental Practices in Summative Evaluation. <i>Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research</i> , 51(1), 103–117.
192	Smith & Tillema	2008	The challenge of assessing portfolios In search of criteria	Balancing Dilemmas in Assessment and Learning in Contemporary Education	Smith, K., & Tillema, H. (2008). The challenge of assessing portfolios In search of criteria. <i>Balancing Dilemmas in Assessment and Learning in Contemporary Education</i> , 183–195.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
193	Snoeyink & Meyer	2007	Shaping Teacher Candidates' Digital Portfolios: What Administrators Want for Hiring	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Snoeyink, R., & Meyer, J. (2007). Shaping Teacher Candidates' Digital Portfolios: What Administrators Want for Hiring. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 23(3), 89–96.
194	Sorin	2005	Webfolio - Using Electronic Portfolios in Preservice Teacher Education	Australian Journal of Teacher Education	Sorin, R. (2005). Webfolio - Using Electronic Portfolios in Preservice Teacher Education. <i>Australian Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 30(1). 27–36.
195	Spendlove	2006	Using "Electronic Portfolios" to Challenge Current Orthodoxies in the Presentation of an Initial Teacher Training Design and Technology Activity	International Journal of Technology and Design Education	Spendlove, D. (2006). Using "Electronic Portfolios" to Challenge Current Orthodoxies in the Presentation of an Initial Teacher Training Design and Technology Activity. <i>International Journal of Technology and Design Education</i> , 16(2), 177–191.
196	Strakova	2016	A critical look at the portfolio as a tool for teacher cognition at pre-gradual level: perceptions of students	Journal of Language and Cultural Education	Strakova, Z. (2016). A critical look at the portfolio as a tool for teacher cognition at pre-gradual level: perceptions of students. <i>Journal of Language and Cultural Education</i> , 4(3), 71–85.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
197	Strawhecker, Messersmith & Balcom	2008	The Role of Electronic Portfolios in the Hiring of K-12 Teachers	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Strawhecker, J., Messersmith, K., & Balcom, A. (2008). The Role of Electronic Portfolios in the Hiring of K-12 Teachers. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 24(2), 65–71.
198	Strijbos, Meeus & Libotton	2007	Portfolio Assignments in Teacher Education: A Tool for Self-Regulating the Learning Process?	International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning	Strijbos, J., Meeus, W., & Libotton, A. (2007). Portfolio Assignments in Teacher Education: A Tool for Self-Regulating the Learning Process? <i>International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning</i> , 1(2), 1–16.
199	Strudler & Wetzel	2005	The Diffusion of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Issues of Initiation and Implementation	Journal of Research on Technology in Education	Strudler, N., & Wetzel, K. (2005). The Diffusion of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Issues of Initiation and Implementation. <i>Journal of Research on Technology in Education</i> , 37(4), 411–433.
200	Strudler & Wetzel	2008	Costs and Benefits of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Faculty Perspectives	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Strudler, N., & Wetzel, K. (2008). Costs and Benefits of Electronic Portfolios in Teacher Education: Faculty Perspectives. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 24(4), 135–142.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
201	Struyven, Dochy & Janssens	2008	The Effects of Hands-On Experience on Students' Preferences for Assessment Methods	Journal of Teacher Education	Struyven, K., Dochy, F., & Janssens, S. (2008). The Effects of Hands-On Experience on Students' Preferences for Assessment Methods. <i>Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 59(1), 69–88.
202	Struyven, Dochy & Janssens	2012	Explaining students' appraisal of lectures and student-activating teaching: perceived context and student characteristics	Interactive Learning Environments	Struyven, K., Dochy, F., & Janssens, S. (2012). Explaining students' appraisal of lectures and student-activating teaching: perceived context and student characteristics. <i>Interactive Learning Environments</i> , 20(5), 391–422.
203	Struyven, & De Roeck	2014	The electronic portfolio as a tool to develop and assess pre-service student teaching competences: Challenges for quality	Studies in Educational Evaluation	Struyven, K. B., Y. , & De Roeck, V. (2014). The electronic portfolio as a tool to develop and assess pre-service student teaching competences: Challenges for quality. <i>Studies in Educational Evaluation</i> , 43, 40–54.
204	Su Bergil & Sariçoban	2018	Utilizing the EPOSTL for English Language Teacher Education Process: Needs and Gains	International Online Journal of Education and Teaching	Su Bergil, A., & Sariçoban, A. (2018). Utilizing the EPOSTL for English Language Teacher Education Process: Needs and Gains. <i>International Online Journal of Education and Teaching</i> , 5(4), 1007–1029.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
205	Sulzen	2011	Identifying Evidence of Reflective Ability in Preservice Teacher Electronic Portfolios	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Sulzen, J. (2011). Identifying Evidence of Reflective Ability in Preservice Teacher Electronic Portfolios. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 19(2), 209–237.
206	Sunal, McCormick, Sunal & Shwery	2005	Elementary Teacher Candidates' Construction of Criteria for Selecting Social Studies Lesson Plans for Electronic Portfolios	Journal of Social Studies Research	Sunal, C. S., McCormick, T., Sunal, D. W., & Shwery, C. (2005). Elementary Teacher Candidates' Construction of Criteria for Selecting Social Studies Lesson Plans for Electronic Portfolios. <i>Journal of Social Studies Research</i> , 29(1), 7–17.
207	Swan	2009	Information Systems in Teacher Preparation Programs: What Can We Learn from a 5-Year Longitudinal Case Study of an Electronic Portfolio Database?	Journal of Educational Computing Research	Swan, G. (2009). Information Systems in Teacher Preparation Programs: What Can We Learn from a 5-Year Longitudinal Case Study of an Electronic Portfolio Database? <i>Journal of Educational Computing Research</i> , 41(4), 431–451.
208	Swan	2009	Examining Barriers in Faculty Adoption of an E-Portfolio System	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Swan, G. (2009). Examining Barriers in Faculty Adoption of an E-Portfolio System. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 25(5), 627–644.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
209	Swan	2009	Tools for Data-Driven Decision Making in Teacher Education: Designing a Portal to Conduct Field Observation Inquiry	Journal of Computing in Teacher Education	Swan, G. (2009). Tools for Data-Driven Decision Making in Teacher Education: Designing a Portal to Conduct Field Observation Inquiry. <i>Journal of Computing in Teacher Education</i> , 25(3), 107–113.
210	Swanson & Hildebrandt	2017	Communicative Learning Outcomes and World Language edTPA: Characteristics of High-scoring Portfolios	Hispania-a Journal Devoted to the Teaching of Spanish and Portuguese	Swanson, P., & Hildebrandt, S. A. (2017). Communicative Learning Outcomes and World Language edTPA: Characteristics of High-scoring Portfolios. <i>Hispania-a Journal Devoted to the Teaching of Spanish and Portuguese</i> , 100(3), 331–347.
211	Syafei	2012	Backwash Effects of Portfolio Assessment in Academic Writing Classes	TEFLIN Journal	Syafei, M. (2012). Backwash Effects of Portfolio Assessment in Academic Writing Classes. <i>TEFLIN Journal</i> , 23(2), 206–221.
212	Tang & Lam	2014	Building an effective online learning community (OLC) in blog-based teaching portfolios	Internet and Higher Education	Tang, E., & Lam, C. (2014). Building an effective online learning community (OLC) in blog-based teaching portfolios. <i>Internet and Higher Education</i> , 20, 79–85.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
213	Taylor, Dunbar-Hall & Rowley	2012	The E-Portfolio Continuum: Discovering Variables for E-Portfolio Adoption within Music Education	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Taylor, J., Dunbar-Hall, P., & Rowley, J. (2012). The E-Portfolio Continuum: Discovering Variables for E-Portfolio Adoption within Music Education. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 28(8), 1362–1381.
214	Thomas & Liu	2012	The Performance of Reflection: A Grounded Analysis of Prospective Teachers' ePortfolios	Journal of Technology and Teacher Education	Thomas, M. K., & Liu, K. (2012). The Performance of Reflection: A Grounded Analysis of Prospective Teachers' ePortfolios. <i>Journal of Technology and Teacher Education</i> , 20(3), 305–330.
215	Thompson Long & Hall	2015	R-NEST: Design-Based Research for Technology-Enhanced Reflective Practice in Initial Teacher Education	Australasian Journal of Educational Technology	Thompson Long, B., & Hall, T. (2015). R-NEST: Design-Based Research for Technology-Enhanced Reflective Practice in Initial Teacher Education. <i>Australasian Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 31(5), 572–596.
216	Tillema & Smith	2007	Portfolio Appraisal: In Search of Criteria	Teaching and Teacher Education	Tillema, H., & Smith, K. (2007). Portfolio Appraisal: In Search of Criteria. <i>Teaching and Teacher Education</i> , 23(4), 442–456.
217	Toom, Husu & Patrikainen	2015	Student Teachers' Patterns of Reflection in the Context of Teaching Practice	European Journal of Teacher Education	Toom, A., Husu, J., & Patrikainen, S. (2015). Student Teachers' Patterns of Reflection in the Context of Teaching Practice. <i>European Journal of Teacher Education</i> , 38(3), 320–340.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
218	Totter & Wyss	2019	Opportunities and Challenges of E-Portfolios in Teacher Education. Lessons Learnt	Research on Education and Media	Totter, A., & Wyss, C. (2019). Opportunities and Challenges of E-Portfolios in Teacher Education. Lessons Learnt. <i>Research on Education and Media</i> , 11(1), 69–75.
219	Trent & Shroff	2013	Technology, Identity, and Community: The Role of Electronic Teaching Portfolios in Becoming a Teacher	Technology, Pedagogy and Education	Trent, J., & Shroff, R. H. (2013). Technology, Identity, and Community: The Role of Electronic Teaching Portfolios in Becoming a Teacher. <i>Technology, Pedagogy and Education</i> , 22(1), 3–20.
220	Tur, Marín, Moreno, Gallardo & Urbina	2016	From Diagrams to Self-Regulated Learning: Student Teachers' Reflections on the Construction of Their PLE	Educational Media International	Tur, G., Marín, V. I., Moreno, J., Gallardo, A., & Urbina, S. (2016). From Diagrams to Self-Regulated Learning: Student Teachers' Reflections on the Construction of Their PLE. <i>Educational Media International</i> , 53(2), 139–152.
221	Tur & Urbina	2014	Blogs as Eportfolio Platforms in Teacher Education: Affordances and Limitations Derived from Student Teachers' Perceptions and Performance on Their Eportfolios	Digital Education Review	Tur, G., & Urbina, S. (2014). Blogs as Eportfolio Platforms in Teacher Education: Affordances and Limitations Derived from Student Teachers' Perceptions and Performance on Their Eportfolios. <i>Digital Education Review</i> , 1–23.

No.	Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal	Reference
222	Tur & Urbina	2016	Collaboration in ePortfolios with Web 2.0 tools in initial teacher training	Cultura Y Educacion	Tur, G., & Urbina, S. (2016). Collaboration in ePortfolios with Web 2.0 tools in initial teacher training. <i>Cultura Y Educacion</i> , 28(3), 601–632.
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Note: $N = 246$ texts.

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